

Toruń, 3 december 2015 r.

Mr.

Dr. Tobias C. Hinse

*Korea Astronomy and
Space Science Institute*

On behalf of the students Secondary School Academic I would like to thank you for an interesting meeting and lecture on astronomy and astrophysics.

Thank you for your time.

I wish you continued success and personal research.

Sincerely!

Dyrektor
Gimnazjum i Liceum Akademickiego

Arkadiusz Stańczyk
mgr Arkadiusz Stańczyk

Torun Science Highschool in the city of Torun, Poland

Date: 03. december 2015

